

Development of a Technique to Measure Voltages on CFRP Surfaces during Lightning Direct Effects Testing

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1. ABSTRACT

This paper demonstrates the successful development of an easy-to-implement technique for measuring voltages on Carbon Fibre Reinforced Plastic (CFRP) surfaces during Lightning Direct Effects (LDE) testing, with careful management of two key aspects - control of electromagnetic interference and electrical contact with the CFRP surface. The work verified that careful minimisation of the size of voltage measurement loops effectively rendered inductive coupling to a negligible level. Readily available off-the-shelf oscilloscope probes were proven to be a suitable choice, provided that a simple digital Low Pass Filter (LPF) was used to remove high-frequency noise from measurements. An epoxy-based method of attaching measurement electrodes to exposed carbon fibres on the CFRP surface was demonstrated to be a suitable choice for both DC and lightning strike testing, whereas a screw-based method was found to be suitable only for DC testing. Simple resin abrasion using emery paper, a milling machine, and a multimeter to determine the point of fibre exposure was demonstrated to be effective to make electrical contact with the surface carbon fibres.

2. INTRODUCTION

Voltage measurements are often desirable in high current LDE tests in order to characterise parameters that influence particular LDE phenomena. For example, Evans et al. [1] measured the voltage between a test fastener and its current return connection to identify the lightning waveform components relevant to the generation of outgassing phenomena in Zone 2A.

There may also be instances which require voltage measurements to be taken directly on the surface of a CFRP component, for example, to quantify the voltage developed along the Inner Mould Line (IML) of a stringer-cover interface. More generally speaking, developing such a capability is necessary in order to anticipate potential breakdown of voltages or thermal sparks between parts that are directly bonded onto the IML. Given the current technological trends geared towards limiting the use of fasteners, integration of composite parts by means of bonding principles, either with or without adhesives, is expected to become more commonplace. From a lightning protection perspective, in order to establish reliable and optimised lightning protection rules, the nature and strength of the electrical threat these internal elements can be exposed to must first be understood. This threat is defined primarily as a voltage, which itself is driven by the voltage gradient on the IML, developed as a result of a strike impacting the Outer Mould Line (OML) of the cover. Potential non-linearities occurring near the impact point can

make this gradient difficult to predict. Direct characterisation with bespoke experiments is therefore perceived as an important first step. Such a characterisation can also enable the development of a complementary simulation capability in support of engineering activities.

However, measuring voltages on CFRP surfaces during high-current lightning tests is challenging for two main reasons: electromagnetic interference, particularly the management of induced voltages on the measurement equipment; and difficulty in achieving adequate electrical contact between the voltage measurement electrodes and the CFRP surface.

Investigations of voltage measurements at fastener joints by Evans [2] revealed that there are different methods to reliably measure voltages in high-current environments. One option is to add a second ‘floating’ measurement loop which follows the same path as the main measurement loop and captures the voltage induced by inductive coupling, which can then be subtracted from the main measurement during post-processing. However, this can become cumbersome and lead to setup errors due to the additional space and time taken for setup. Accordingly, the preferable option is to devise a technique which is inherently immune to inductive coupling.

In order to attach voltage measurement electrodes to the CFRP surface, the electrically non-conductive surface resin layer must first be removed to expose and subsequently establish electrical contact with the conductive carbon fibres of the surface ply [3]. But in the resin removal process, care must simultaneously be taken to ensure that damage to the surface fibres themselves is avoided, as CFRP resistance depends on fibre volume [4]. Accordingly, there are several factors to take into consideration in the determination of the resin removal method.

Firstly, whilst several methods for resin removal have been reported, particularly in the case of CFRP recycling, processes such as microwave irradiation [5], pyrolysis [6], fluidised bed technology [7], solvolysis [8], and near-critical and supercritical fluid-based processes [9] all exploit the material differences between the carbon fibres and the resin. As the aim in this context is to remove only the surface resin and not all the resin in the sample, these methods are therefore not suitable. A mechanical procedure which utilises readily available workshop tools such as milling machines is favoured over more complex processes such as laser ablation [10] in order to achieve the aim of developing a measurement technique which is easily implementable.

Secondly, due to the transparency of resin, it is not possible to examine the target location directly under a microscope

to identify the exact depth at which the carbon fibres are exposed [11].

Thirdly, although CFRP laminates have nominal parameters such as the Cured Ply Thickness and fibre to resin ratio, due to the nature of the manufacturing process, there is a degree of variability, which must be taken into account.

To make electrical contact with exposed surface fibres, different electrode formation methods have been utilised for purposes such as the Electrical-Resistance-Change-Method used for smart-sensing under loading conditions [12]. Electric Copper plating was utilised by Todoroki et al. [13] and sintering of metal nano-inks using white-flashlight irradiation was performed by Takahashi et al. [14]. However, a simpler method of contact is preferable in order to achieve the aim of developing a measurement technique that is easy to implement. Whilst the method of silk screening using conductive Silver paint explored by Abid [4] is in theory easier to implement than the aforementioned approaches, soldering of thin strands of wire onto the metalised area using Lead-based low temperature solder brings about challenges of preventing degradation of the Silver paint, as well as health and safety risk management due to the Lead content.

This paper describes a novel and easy-to-implement technique of accurately measuring voltages on CFRP surfaces during LDE testing, which could potentially be adopted as a widespread laboratory technique.

3. CONTROL OF ELECTROMAGNETIC INTERFERENCE

In order to devise a measurement technique which is inherently immune to inductive coupling, specific tests were performed by varying the following: measurement loop size, voltage measurement probe, and current attachment method.

3.1 Experimental Approach

$$V(t) = R_s i(t) + L_s \frac{di(t)}{dt} + M \frac{di(t)}{dt} \quad (1)$$

In LDE testing, the CFRP sample can be represented by a resistor, R_s and an inductor, L_s in series. The measured voltage drop across the sample, V , can be represented as the sum of three terms as described in (1), where $i(t)$ corresponds to current as a function of time, $\frac{di(t)}{dt}$ corresponds to current differentiated with respect to time, and M corresponds to the mutual inductance between the sample and the measurement loop. Whilst the terms $R_s i(t)$ and $L_s \frac{di(t)}{dt}$ (referred to henceforth as ‘resistive’ and ‘inductive’ voltage drops respectively) form the actual voltage drop to be measured, $M \frac{di(t)}{dt}$ corresponds to the voltage drop due to parasitic inductive coupling which must be eliminated. In accordance with Faraday’s Law, inductive coupling can be minimised if the measurement loop can be set up such that the wiring runs as close to the sample as possible along the current path, as this would minimise flux linkage [15].

A test sample with a known resistance of 21.24 mΩ and negligible inductance was produced such that the desired voltage drop due to the first two terms in (1) could be deduced from the current excitation waveform. Any deviation in the measurement from this expectation would then be due to inductive coupling.

Loops were set up to obtain two measurements: V_2 was laid out to measure the actual voltage drop across the resistor, and V_3 was its corresponding ‘floating’ loop which followed the same path but captured only the voltage induced by inductive coupling as it had no electrical contact with the test sample. In order to investigate the influence of loop size on inductive coupling, two setups were designed as shown in Fig. 1:

Fig. 1. Test Setups (a) A and (b) B

In Setup A, both V_2 and V_3 loops were placed flat against the test setup using insulating tape. In order to ensure that the V_3 loop followed the path created by the V_2 loop, one half of the former was taped to the latter, and the other half was taped to the circuit itself, as the V_2 loop was closed by the resistor-based circuit. In Setup B, the loop size of V_2 was increased to study the effect of loop size on susceptibility to inductive coupling. The loop size of V_3 was accordingly also increased to ensure it followed the loop of V_2 .

For each test setup, two types of voltage measurement probes were used. In the first instance, off-the-shelf probes were connected to the measurement leads as shown in Fig. 1. In the second instance, the leads were connected to voltage dividers at the oscilloscope. Additionally, two methods of current attachment at the metal plate were used: arc and conducted. The reason for this was to characterise the influence of high-frequency noise on the measurement that is usually more prominent in arc attachment tests. Currents were measured using a Rogowski coil for all test shots. The resultant test matrix is shown below in Table 1:

Table 1. Matrix of test shots

	Off-the-shelf Probe	Voltage Divider	
Setup A	Shot 1	Shot 7	Conducted Current
	Shot 2	Shot 8	Arc Attachment
Setup B	Shot 3	Shot 5	Conducted Current
	Shot 4	Shot 6	Arc Attachment

3.2 Experimental Results

Fig. 2 shows an example set of the measurements which enabled the initial verification that V_2 was in phase with current, and V_3 with the derivative of current:

Fig. 2. Shot 1 (a) current (b) V_1 – disregarded in analysis (c) V_2 (d) V_3 (e) derivative of current (f) current and scaled V_2 (g) derivative of current and scaled V_3

As shown by Fig. 2(f) where V_2 was scaled up to match the peak of the current waveform, V_2 is precisely synchronous with current, which demonstrates resistive behaviour and negligible inductance. Similarly, V_3 , which was scaled up to match the peak of the current derivative waveform, is synchronous with the current derivative (Fig. 2(g)), which conforms to expectations as V_3 corresponds to the $M \frac{di(t)}{dt}$ term (1).

Fig. 3 shows V_2 and current measurements from four test shots.

Fig. 3. Filtered measurements to compare probe performance (a) V_2 – Shots 1 and 7 (b) Current – Shots 1 and 7 (c) V_2 – Shots 3 and 5 (d) Current – Shots 3 and 5 (e) V_2 – Shots 4 and 6 (f) Current – Shots 4 and 6 (g) V_2 – Shots 2 and 8 (h) Current – Shots 2 and 8

Fig. 3(a, e) shows excellent agreement between measurements of both probe types. Apparent variation in measurements from the two probes in Fig. 3(c, g) is verified to be due to variation in the current injected (Fig. 3(d, h)). Fig. 3(e, g) which corresponds to arc attachment shows a small spike just before the actual start of the V_2 waveform which is not evident in Fig. 3(a, c). However, this spike is also present in the current measurements (Fig. 3(f, h)), which indicates that this is likely to be a high-frequency artefact, and is accordingly not introduced by the measurement equipment or setups. This is further verified by the fact that it is present in arc attachment tests of both loop sizes and both probe types. Therefore, both probes can be deemed to be suitable choices in all tested configurations.

Fig. 4(a) illustrates the presence of high-frequency noise at the start of the unfiltered V_2 waveform for the arc attachment test using off-the-shelf probes, which is not present in the voltage divider counterpart (Fig. 4(c)):

Fig. 4. Zoomed in graphs of V_2 (a) Unfiltered waveforms – Shots 1 and 2 (b) Filtered waveforms – Shots 1 and 2 (c) Unfiltered waveforms – Shots 7 and 8 (d) Filtered waveforms – Shots 7 and 8

An error in setting up loops is unlikely to be the reason as this occurrence is present in off-the-shelf probe measurements involving both loop sizes. Regardless, Fig. 4(b) shows that filtration using a LPF with a cut-off frequency of 1 MHz successfully eliminates this influence. Furthermore, this occurrence is not present with conducted current tests. This conforms with expectations as arc attachments cause greater electromagnetic interference [16][17].

Fig. 5 shows filtered V_3 for the arc attachment tests with off-the-shelf probes, where the larger loop's waveform peak (43.6 V) is over 16 times higher than that of the smaller loop (2.7 V). This confirms the influence of the loop size. Since the peak of V_3 for the minimised loop size is only 0.4% of the peak of V_2 (694 V), inductive coupling is deemed to be negligible for this setup.

Fig. 5. Filtered V_3 – Shots 2 and 4

To further illustrate the influence of this inductive coupling on the voltage measurement curve, Fig. 6 compares the filtered voltage measurement waveform (V_2) with only the resistive component of the voltage ($R_s i(t)$). The resistive component is constructed by first dividing the voltage at the time of peak current (*when* $\frac{di(t)}{dt} = 0$) by the peak current

Whilst, in theory, only one ply of CFRP was required for the purpose of the test, practically, as the lack of structural rigidity in a single ply would have resulted in handling difficulties (e.g., fixing to a test rig), 45 plies of Glass Fibre Reinforced Polymer (GFRP) were added underneath to improve rigidity. In order to expose carbon fibres, surface resin was removed from the measurement locations, according to the method outlined in Section 4.1.1.

Two plates of aerospace-grade Aluminium alloy were clamped down onto the abraded edges using G-clamps on each edge to form the current injection and extraction electrodes. Prior to attaching Aluminium plates, the abraded edges on the CFRP sample were first metallised with Silver paint to facilitate uniform current injection across the width of the panel. Three screw-based contacts were then attached to the measurement locations A1, A2 and A3, and three epoxy-based contacts to B1, B2 and B3.

The test sample was subjected to various current injections, both DC and scaled Waveform A (WF-A), as shown below in Table 2:

Table 2. Specifications of test shots (Shots 1 and 2 are baseline shots)

Current Type:	DC		WF-A																
Nominal Peak Current (A):	5		1000	1500	2000	3000	4000	5000	1500										
Row:	A	B	B	A	A	B	B	A	A	B	B	A	A	B	B	A			
Test Shot Number:	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16			
Measurements:	Current Injected, V_1, V_2, V_3																		

Current Type:	DC																												
Nominal Peak Current (A):	1	2	5	8	10	20	30	40	50	60	80	100	5																
Row:	A	B	B	A	A	B	B	A	A	B	B	A	A	B	B	A	A	B	B	A									
Test Shot Number:	17	18	19	20	21	22	23	24	25	26	27	28	29	30	31	32	33	34	35	36	37	38	39	40	41	42			
Measurements:	Current Injected, V_1, V_2, V_3																												

Injected current, V_1 , V_2 and V_3 , were measured for each injection. Rogowski coils were used to measure the scaled WF-A current, and off-the-shelf oscilloscope probes were used to measure voltages. Although a current-sensing resistor was added to measure the injected DC current, due to the low Signal to Noise Ratio, the nominal current level as per the DC power supply was used for the analysis. As a single test sample was used for multiple test shots, a thermal camera was used to monitor the temperature to ensure that no thermal degradation of the sample and subsequent modifications of its electrical characteristics would take place. Following detection of temperature increase (as small as 1 °C), the sample was allowed to return to ambient temperature prior to resuming testing.

Theoretical Analysis

Fig. 10 is a circuit schematic of the test sample:

Fig. 10. Simplified circuit diagram

For the purpose of analysis, the CFRP ply has been represented by a set of resistors (assuming negligible contribution due to self and mutual inductance during scaled WF-A testing). R_{C1} and R_{C2} correspond to the contact resistances between the CFRP ply and the ‘Current In’ and ‘Current Out’ metal plates respectively. $R_{CFRP-A1}$ through $R_{CFRP-A4}$ respectively correspond to the parts of the panel resistance along Row A between the inner edge of the ‘Current In’ plate and A1, between A1 and A2, between A2 and A3; and between A4 and the inner edge of the ‘Current Out’ plate (Fig. 9). $R_{CFRP-B1}$ through $R_{CFRP-B4}$ similarly correspond to the resistances along Row B. I corresponds to the total current supplied, and I_a and I_b correspond to the current flowing along Rows A and B. The contact resistances between the voltage measurement electrodes and the CFRP sample in the parallel branches can be disregarded, as no current will flow into this parallel branch due to the large input impedance of the oscilloscope. Assuming Rows A and B are electrically identical owing to their symmetrical spacing with respect to the sample axis and their equivalent geometries, ‘measured’ resistances R_1 , R_2 and R_3 can be calculated as follows:

$$R_1 = \frac{V_1}{I} \quad (2)$$

$$R_2 = \frac{V_2}{I_a} = \frac{V_2}{I_b} \quad (3)$$

$$R_3 = \frac{V_3}{I_a} = \frac{V_3}{I_b} \quad (4)$$

As the clamping of metal plates and metallisation of exposed carbon fibres at the current injection site are assumed to ensure uniform current injection across the width of the CFRP ply, the following ratio can be used to estimate the current distributed along Rows A and B:

$$\frac{I_a}{I} = \frac{I_b}{I} = \frac{w_1}{w_2} = \frac{0.01 \text{ m}}{0.3 \text{ m}} = \frac{1}{30} \quad (5)$$

where w_1 and w_2 are respectively the width of either Row A or B (which is equivalent to the diameter of the measurement locations on each Row), and the nominal width of the CFRP ply. The theoretical resistance of the CFRP sample can be calculated as follows:

$$R_{CFRPtot} = 8.63 \times 10^{-2} \Omega \quad (6)$$

Analytical estimates for R_1 , R_2 and R_3 can be calculated as follows:

$$R_{1_Analytical} = R_{CFRPtot} + R_{C1} + R_{C2} \quad (7)$$

$$R_{2_Analytical} = \frac{l_2}{\sigma w_1 t} \quad (8)$$

$$R_{3_Analytical} = \frac{l_3}{\sigma w_1 t} \quad (9)$$

where σ is the nominal electrical conductivity along the fibre direction (x-direction) and is $3.8 \times 10^3 \text{ S/m}$; l_1 , l_2 and l_3 are distances between electrodes; and t is the thickness of the CFRP ply.

Experimental Results

Figs 11 and 12 show examples of DC and scaled WF-A test results respectively. The overshoots observed in Fig. 11 correspond to the turn on transient in the current.

Fig. 11. Test Shot 18 (a) Current (b) V_1 (c) V_2 (d) V_3

Fig. 12. Shot 13 (a) Current (b) V_1 (c) V_2 (d) V_3

Fig. 13 shows ‘measured’ R_1 (calculated by dividing V_1 at the time of peak current (when $\frac{di(t)}{dt} = 0$) by the peak current), as well as $R_{CFRPtot}$ (as R_{C1} and R_{C2} are not known to compute $R_{1_Analytical}$).

Fig. 13. R_1 against logarithmic current - arrows denote testing sequence

In the legend, the word “during” is highlighted as the V_1 measurement does not directly utilise either of the two contact methods, as the measurement is obtained across the metal plates on the left and right-hand side edges by directly clipping on off-the-shelf probes. The two data points circled by the purple line correspond to the first two 5 A DC baseline shots. The results of the next set of tests (scaled WF-A), are circled with the blue dashed line, where a decreasing resistance with subsequent tests of increasing current can be observed by the curve-fit. This is likely due to the decreasing of contact resistances at the interfaces between the CFRP and edge metal plates with increasing current, similar to observations in other studies of contact resistance modification with lightning current [2]. A possible explanation for this is that the current flow causes a rapid localised temperature rise at the CFRP-metal interface, which softens the contact materials, thus leading to an increase in the number of “electrically conductive a-

spots”, therefore forming a stronger contact. Higher currents lead to more Joule heating and therefore greater temperature rise [18]. If the current levels are further increased, the contact resistance will become negligible, and thus, R_1 will converge to the CFRP resistance [2]. The measurements appear to converge to the estimated R_{CFRP} value at approximately 3.6 kA, but then proceeds to decrease further. This drop below the estimated value is likely to be due to the discrepancies between the nominal and actual values used for the estimation. The cluster circled by the dotted green line corresponds to the final set of shots (DC). These have a median of 0.12Ω , and are seen to follow a reasonably straight line which conforms to Ohm’s Law. There is a difference of 24.1 to 38.1 mΩ between the lowest and highest data points, and $R_{CFRPtot}$. Whilst differences between nominal and actual values of material parameters (e.g., ply conductivity) could have some influence, this discrepancy is most likely caused by a partial regaining of contact resistance at metal-CFRP interfaces in the absence of high-current injections, considering the test sequence.

Similar to R_1 , R_2 (Fig. 14(a)) and R_3 (Fig. 14(b)) data points were also respectively obtained by dividing V_2 and V_3 at the time of peak current (when $\frac{di(t)}{dt} = 0$) by $\frac{1}{30}th$ of the peak current.

Fig. 14. (a) R_2 and (b) R_3 - both against logarithmic current

R_2 and R_3 data points from DC shots have medians of 1.198 Ω and 606.8 mΩ respectively, and follow a reasonably straight zero-gradient line (Fig. 14). Whilst there is a difference between the analytical and ‘measured’ values in the range of 45.1 mΩ to 298.1 mΩ for R_2 and 7.3 mΩ to 138.8 mΩ for R_3 , these differences are likely due to differences between nominal and actual values of CFRP parameters as discussed afore. Unlike R_1 , where the contact resistance between the CFRP and metal electrodes are included in the V_1 measurement, the V_2 and V_3 measurements are in direct contact with the CFRP and very little current is drawn through this contact. Therefore, the decreasing resistance with increasing current during scaled WF-A tests cannot be attributed to a modification of a contact resistance. Further investigations are required to understand the reasons for this non-linearity.

Fig. 15 shows the ratio of (V_2/V_3) (equivalent to (R_2/R_3)) for all shots. and their percentage errors:

Fig. 15. Graphs of (a) V_2/V_3 ratio against logarithmic current and (b) percentage error of V_2/V_3 ratio against logarithmic current

Ratios from DC shots show excellent alignment with the analytical ratio with a maximum percentage difference of less than 4%. Results from scaled WF-A shots display scatter in both plots, as well as indication of a potential non-linear trend of a decreasing ratio with increasing current, particularly for the screw-based contacts, but this cannot be confirmed due to the limited number of data points. Given the fact that both contact methods yielded percentage errors of less than 4% for DC shots, it can be concluded that both contact methods are suitable for DC levels.

4.2.2 High Level Lightning Currents

Following DC and low level lightning tests, contact methods were next evaluated with higher level lightning current tests in order to select the best method.

Experimental Approach

Fig. 16 below shows the test setup schematics:

Fig. 16. (a) Test Setup (b) Schematic of fastener stack (c) Length and width of stack

The theory behind this test is the same as that behind the DC and low level lightning current-based testing counterpart (Section 4.2.1). In order to reduce the voltage to a measurable value (less than 2500 V as per instrument ratings), the CFRP sample was modified by adding more plies to increase the thickness, therefore reducing the resistance of the sample (8). For unidirectional laminates, Angelidis *et al.* [20] found that the through-thickness conductivity could effectively be neglected. Therefore, such laminates can be modelled as a network of parallel resistors, with each parallel branch corresponding to a ply. The decision was accordingly made to use a unidirectional CFRP laminate with 12 plies as resistance is inversely proportional to the cross-sectional area (therefore enabling increased current flow and development of lower voltages), as well as to enable theoretical prediction of results prior to testing. Surface resin was removed according to the method outlined in Section 4.1.1, from the six circular measurement locations indicated in light blue in Fig. 16(a). In order to inject current as uniformly as possible into all plies and ensure that the top and bottom plies of the sample would not become preferential paths, e.g., due to contact with the conductive nut, a series of conductive fasteners was assembled on each edge in interference fit to facilitate current flow, and the sample was sandwiched between two layers of insulating glass fibre. The series of fasteners on each side was equipotentialised via a metal plate. The stack

arrangement through which 12 fasteners on each side were assembled is shown in Fig. 16(b) and the dimensions of the stack are shown in Fig. 16(c). For the screw-based contacts, Copper foil of thickness 0.2 mm was used following the observation in the tests conducted as outlined in Section 4.2.1, whereupon finally dismantling the test setup, all screws along Row A were found to have perforated the 0.1 mm thick Copper as shown below in Fig. 17. It is worth noting that this was deemed to not have had an impact on measurements, as the circle of foil directly under the screw would have remained in place and in electrical contact with the rest of the Copper foil until dismantling.

Fig. 17. Perforation of Copper

An assembly error meant that the second panel was assembled with 10 fasteners instead of 12 on each side, with the same pitch as in Fig. 16(a) but a distance to edge of 35.7 mm. The consequences of this will be addressed in the results analysis.

Table 3 shows the details of the test shots:

Table 3. Test Matrix ('Location' column syntax – X.Y where X corresponds to Panel number and Y corresponds to Row letter)

Test Shot No.	Location	Peak Current (kA)	Test Shot No.	Location	Peak Current (kA)
1	1.A	1	14	2.B	1
2	1.B - Baseline Shot	1	15	2.A - Baseline Shot	1
3	1.A	1	16	2.B	1
4	1.B - Baseline Shot	1	17	2.A - Baseline Shot	1
5	1.A	5	18	2.B	5
6	1.A	10	19	2.B	10
7	1.A	20	20	2.B	20
8	1.A	40	21	2.B	40
9	1.A	60	22	2.B	60
10	1.A	70	23	2.B	70
11	1.A	1	24	2.B	1
12	1.B - Baseline Shot	1	25	2.A - Baseline Shot	1
13	Panel 1	100 (Arc)	26	Panel 2	100 (Arc)

Test Shot 13 and 26 correspond to arc attachments with a peak of 100 kA which were injected to the CFRP on the surface opposite to that of the measurements. This was to assess the mechanical robustness of the contact methods in the presence of shock waves and magnetic forces caused by a full-scale lightning current. The voltage measurement equipment was disconnected from the oscilloscope for this test.

All measurements were accordingly made with only conducted current tests, as, other than to assess the mechanical robustness, the type of current injected has no bearing on the aim of this test.

Whilst both contact methods were tested on the same laminate under Section 4.2.1 due to the lower levels of current injected, this was not deemed appropriate for higher current levels due to the strong likelihood of conditioning of the laminate. Accordingly, two laminates were produced as discussed afore to test the two different contact methods. However, due to the possible differences in material and therefore in electrical characteristics between the two panels (in addition to the variation in the number of fasteners), several baseline shots were included to enable comparison of contact methods on the same panel (Table 3).

The method of minimising inductive coupling, outlined in Section 3, was applied for V_1 , V_2 and V_3 measurement loops. Although the results under Section 3.2 verified that a calibration loop to measure inductive coupling was not required for this method, as an additional step, V_1 , V_2 and V_3 were coupled with calibration loops to measure voltages induced by inductive coupling - V_4 , V_5 and V_6 respectively - in order to experimentally demonstrate the validity of the method when injecting lightning current into CFRP samples. The results indicated that the percentage of inductive coupling of all measurements was less than 0.4% of the measured peak voltage, and hence, inductive coupling was confirmed to be negligible. Accordingly, V_4 , V_5 and V_6 measurements are disregarded in the main analysis. Current was measured using a Rogowski coil.

Theoretical Analysis

The circuit diagram introduced in Section 4.2.1 (Fig. 10) applies to each ply of the 12-ply laminate, where R_{C1} and R_{C2} are the collective contact resistances between each CFRP ply and the series of fasteners on the Current In and Out sides respectively, and where I corresponds to current injected into a single ply assuming uniform current injection, with $12I$ supplied by the generator. On the surface ply, $\frac{I}{30}$ will then flow along each Row. Using (6), (9) and (10), $R_{CFRPtot}$ (the total panel resistance), $R_{2_Analytical}$ and $R_{3_Analytical}$ can be calculated to be 1.58×10^{-2} , 4.67 and 2.33 Ω respectively, where $R_{2_Analytical}$ is expected to be twice that of $R_{3_Analytical}$. $R_{1_Analytical_PX}$ can be described as follows, where R_{C1tot_PX} and R_{C2tot_PX} are the combined contact resistances between the CFRP sample and the fasteners on the Current In and Out sides respectively, and X denotes the panel number:

$$R_{1_Analytical_PX} = R_{CFRPtot} + R_{C1tot_PX} + R_{C2tot_PX} \quad (10)$$

Experimental Results

Results from ‘baseline’ shots 2, 4, 12, 15, 17 and 25 (Table 3) will be presented separately to those of the ‘main’ shots (excluding arc attachment shots 13 and 26 for which no measurements were made).

The data points outlined by a blue dotted circle in the following figures correspond to an outlier (Shot 12) where the epoxy-based contacts at B1 and B3 (Fig. 16(a)) disconnected from the CFRP sample due to the use of an out-of-date tube of epoxy. Therefore, the results of V_2 and V_3 of this test shot, although included in the graphs, should be ignored.

Fig. 18 shows ‘measured’ R_1 for all test shots, as well as $R_{CFRPtot}$, versus current.

Fig. 18. Graph of R_1 against peak current for (a) main shots and (b) baseline shots. Scatter plots show ‘measured’ resistance calculated with measured voltage and current.

R_1 was calculated by dividing V_1 at the time of peak current (when $\frac{di(t)}{dt} = 0$) by the peak current. The ‘measured’ R_1 data points (Fig. 18(a)) show a trend of decreasing resistance with increasing current which denotes the modification of the contact resistance between the fasteners and the laminate – as discussed in Section 4.2.1. The curves are seen to converge towards $R_{CFRPtot}$. In the drawing of the best-fit curves, the two data points outlined in the solid blue line have been disregarded as these show the return of the residual contact resistance discussed afore in Section 4.2.1. Discrepancy between the measurements of the two panels is likely due to material variations between the panels, as well as difference in R_{C1tot_PX} and R_{C2tot_PX} between the panels due to the difference in the number of fasteners.

Fig. 19 shows the variations of ‘measured’ R_2 and R_3 with respect to measured peak current:

Fig. 19. Graphs against current for (a) R_2 (main shots) (b) R_2 (baseline shots) (c) R_3 (main shots) (d) R_3 (baseline shots)

R_2 and R_3 were calculated by dividing the voltage at the time of peak current (when $\frac{di(t)}{dt} = 0$) by the peak current. Whilst $R_{2_Analytical}$ and $R_{3_Analytical}$ are constant, Fig. 19(a, c) clearly shows that R_2 and R_3 measured using screw-based contacts on Panel 1 follow an exponentially decaying trend with increasing current. This is not observed with the epoxy-based contacts’ measurements, which follow a reasonably straight line with medians of 2.06 and 1.19 Ω respectively for R_2 and R_3 . Whilst this median is less than the analytical values, this is likely due to the fact that the assumption made about uniform current distribution across the width of the sample is not accurate. This is due to the discontinuity posed by the discrete fasteners used for current injection and extraction and the low transverse conductivity. In the case of less-than-uniform current distribution, a current proportion greater than the assumption would flow along each Row, resulting in lower R_2 and R_3 values. Differences between the nominal values used for CFRP parameters and the actual values could also be a contributing factor. Self-inductance is ruled out as the cause for the exponentially decaying trend seen with screw-based contacts as values were extracted at the time of peak current where $\frac{di(t)}{dt}$ is zero. Thermal conditioning of the panel is also unlikely as the temperature was not observed to increase significantly as in Section 4.2.1, and also as it was only observed on one panel.

The cause of the difference in the data points between the two contact methods requires further investigation. Post-test inspection of the screw-based contact method revealed signs of high current transfer to the copper disk in contact with the panel surface (Fig. 20). The contact between the disk and the panel was not expected to play a role because it was in series with the high input impedance of the oscilloscope. However, the scorch marks on the disk are suggestive of a short-circuit via the Copper, thereby creating a parallel path of lower resistance for the current to flow through, thus reducing the voltage measurement. However, for this to be the case, the measurement points of the screw-based method would be expected to start at the same point as the epoxy-based measurement points at lower current levels and diverge below them with increasing current, unlike the convergence towards them observed in Fig. 23(a, c). The results of Shot 11 circled in the solid blue line correspond to the return of the residual contact resistance for the lower level peak of 1 kA.

Fig. 20. Underside of screw-based contacts shows evidence of arcing at interface of Copper with CFRP surface – Panel 1

Fig. 21 shows that the ratio of V_2/V_3 (which is equivalent to R_2/R_3) is very close to the expected ratio of 2, although some scatter and variation can be seen for results from both contact methods. There is no indication of the decreasing trend with current, observed in Fig. 19 for measurements on Panel 1 made with screw-based contacts. This is likely to be because the phenomenon was present in both V_2 and V_3 , which subsequently cancelled one another upon division.

Fig. 21. Graph of V_2/V_3 ratio against peak current for (a) main shots and (b) baseline shots

The corresponding percentage error for the V_2/V_3 ratio is less than 20% overall across both panels and both contact methods, which can be deemed acceptable.

Following the two arc attachment tests (Shots 13 and 26), five out of the six screw-based contacts used on the two panels became disconnected due to shock waves and magnetic forces brought about by the arc attachment, whereas none of the epoxy-based contacts in Panel 2 were disconnected (only the epoxy-based contacts on Panel 2 could be assessed with arc attachment due to the disconnection of the epoxy-based contacts on Panel 1 which was discussed afore). Accordingly, the adhesion of epoxy-based contacts is expected to be suitable in the presence of arcs, provided that manufacturer's instructions are followed in the application of the epoxy.

5. CONCLUSIONS

The aim was to establish an easy-to-implement, calibrated technique of accurately measuring voltages on surface plies of CFRP during lightning tests. The main conclusions against the objectives are twofold:

1. It was found that careful positioning of the measurement leads is required to avoid any influence from inductive coupling on the measurement. Minimising the size of the measurement loops to ensure that they are positioned very close to the test sample effectively reduces influences from inductive coupling to a negligible value, thus eliminating the need for inclusion of cumbersome calibration loops. Off-the-shelf probes were also shown to be a valid option, provided that a simple digital LPF was applied on the results during the post-processing stage to remove high-frequency noise.
2. Out of screw-based and epoxy-based contact methods trialled, epoxy-based contact methods were confirmed to be the superior choice. Further studies can be done to verify the expectation of reliable adhesion if manufacturer's instructions are followed. Whilst removal of resin using emery paper and a milling machine (with the help of a digital multimeter to detect electrical continuity) was found to be effective, greater reliability can potentially be established by inspecting the edge of the laminate through a microscope to gauge the thickness of the surface resin prior to abrasion, and using a depth-controllable milling machine to perform the subsequent abrasion.

The measurement capability presented in this paper could be suitable for use as a widespread standardised laboratory technique. This has been proven to be practicable. This technique will be applicable in various LDE tests, for example, to determine the voltage developed at the IML of the cover in a semi-cured stringer-cover interface during LDE testing. This capability would be particularly useful when testing future advanced wing designs, where co-bonding, co-welding and co-curing technologies will be increasingly utilised instead of fasteners.

6. FURTHER WORK

Electromagnetic simulations can be performed to understand the current flow in the unidirectional panels tested under Section 4.2.2. The measurement technique developed can be applied in tests to understand the evolution of voltages on a CFRP surface during lightning strike testing, and determine the presence/absence of any non-linear voltage gradient development. Further simulations can be performed using both unidirectional and quasi-isotropic representations to complement such test results. Furthermore, the epoxy-based contact method has been validated for a specific type of epoxy by a specific manufacturer. Accordingly, further work would need to be performed to assess the technique's validity for different geometries, and to evaluate different conductive epoxies in order to determine the exact parameters which are instrumental to the method's success (e.g., the range of

acceptable electrical conductivity). Any type of epoxy which meets the specified criteria can then be used to establish electrical contact.

7. REFERENCES

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